

Coordinating data collection in intercropping: A feasible example

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Summary

Intercropping is a promising strategy towards a more sustainable agriculture. To turn research outcomes into practice, integration of results across countries and between research and on-farm trials is necessary. Inadequacy of current data reporting tools (e.g. from biodiversity experiments) to fully accommodate the particularities of intercropping data represents a major barrier to exchange of data on crop mixtures. Here, within the pan-European project ‘DIVERSify’, we give a feasible example of standardisation procedures in data collection and collation in intercropping field trials across Europe, conducted at small, large and on farm scale. A series of data standardisation tools is described, with details on specific adaptations made according to trial scale. Finally, we give recommendations on critical aspects for data coordination and an outlook on the next steps required for making intercropping datasets comparable also at a global scale.

Key words: Intercropping, field trials, crop traits, data standardisation, formatting, open science principles

Introduction

Field experiments on intercropping have increasingly come into fashion over the last years in response to calls for more sustainable cropping strategies. The positive effects of crop diversification on agroecosystem biodiversity and ecosystem functioning have been shown in several studies (Gurr *et al.*, 2003; Hauggaard-Nielsen *et al.*, 2008; Hooks & Johnson, 2003; Kremen & Miles, 2012) competition and facilitation. Field experiments were carried out on a sandy loam soil and a sandy soil in Denmark over three consecutive cropping seasons including dual grain legume (pea, faba bean and lupin. Efficient data exchange is critical for further research progress and for development of new intercropping strategies and technologies. Access and use of intercropping data, however, still present barriers. A frequent issue is that many datasets lack clear semantics and metadata standardisation, and thus remain unpublished and inaccessible to the scientific and agricultural community. On the applied side, a barrier to effective use of intercropping experimental data is often that datasets obtained from small scale trials fail to meet equivalent data obtained

on a commercial scale. As a result, scientific recommendations on crop mixtures often lack larger scale evidence necessary to turn research into practice (Bybee-Finley & Ryan, 2018). A common gap from which such barriers can arise, is the lack of international data standardisation guidelines in intercropping research. Substantial differences in designs and size of experiments, trait names and protocols may discourage from bringing datasets together. Adoption of international guidelines for standardisation and accessibility of research practices, such as Open Science (OS) and FAIR principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) can dramatically accelerate access to higher-quality data and increase the possibility of bringing datasets together.

For instance, several initiatives within the field of biodiversity research have already been put into practice (Gallagher *et al.*, 2020; Gerlach *et al.*, 2014; Wiczorek *et al.*, 2012)

Attempts to standardise research practices have also been carried out in agriculture. The International Consortium for Agricultural Systems has developed guidelines for reporting data standards in agricultural field experiments which have been made flexible to enable data capturing across a variety of management practices and traits (White *et al.*, 2013) leading to investigation where multiple sets of experimental data are examined using tools such as simulation and regression. The use of standard data formats for documenting experiments and modeling crop growth and development can facilitate exchanges of information and software, allowing researchers to focus on research *per se* rather than on converting and re-formatting data or trying to estimate or otherwise compensate for missing information. The standards developed by the International Benchmark Sites Network for Agrotechnology Transfer (IBSNAT). A similar aim at farm level is being carried out by FAOSTAT, by developing international standards and tools for data collection, analysis and disseminating (“FAOSTAT commodity definitions and correspondences lists”, n.d.). Such tools, however, have been mainly designed to accommodate crop monoculture data. In comparison with pure cultures, intercropping data can be rather complex to report, as they carry information not only on the focus crop, but also on the interactions with its neighbouring plants (e.g. competition, facilitation or complementarity). Plastic traits will likely respond to these interactions differently compared to monocultures. Therefore, measured traits should be recorded in order to track back the crop combination in which crops have been growing, and should be comparable to a monoculture grown in similar conditions. A further level of complexity lies in the number of crop species grown together and the seed proportion used, which can dramatically increase the number of combinations to be reported. For these reasons, tools not designed to account for this complexity may be unsuitable for reporting intercropping data.

Up to now, concrete attempts to coordinate intercropping field trials across countries have been lacking. Moreover, in order to turn research recommendations into practice, standardisation protocols should also enable coordination between academic and commercial scale trials. Within the ‘DIVERSify’ project (grant no. 727284, www.plant-teams.eu), on designing novel intercropping solutions, we give a concrete example on coordination of intercropping field experiments and dataset alignment among multiple partners, trial types and years. A set of tools was developed and distributed among project partners to coordinate data collection. Moreover, experimental trials at small, large and on-farm scale were carried out, generating an opportunity to link experimental agroecological data with production-oriented information across pedoclimatic zones.

Materials and Methods

The project aims to test plant teams’ performance in terms of plant agronomic and ecological traits and crop productivity. Trials on crop mixtures were carried out at small-scale, large-scale and on-farm trials covering a total of nine locations across Europe (United Kingdom, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Italy, Portugal and Spain).

Fig. 1. Examples of trials: A and B, large-scale trial with durum wheat and *Trifolium alexandrinum* in Italy 2017; C, large-scale trials with spring oats and clover understory carried in UK 2020; D and E, small-scale trials with faba bean-wheat and pea-barley, Italy 2017 and Germany 2018, respectively. In the German experiment (E), high management input is clearly visible in replicate blocks as a darker shade of green. Pictures kindly shared by Stefano Tavoletti, Jen Bannfield-Zanin and Jan Lehmann.

Experimental set-ups

Small-scale trials collected crop trait data over 2 years (2017–2018). A common experimental set-up was agreed prior to trial start in order to generate comparable outcomes. Split-plot or randomized block designs were adopted when possible (Fig.1. D–E). Crop combinations were tested both under low and conventional agrochemical input, with variations depending on regional recommendations and local necessities. To study trait plasticity, each crop was tested both in mixed and pure stands. Large-scale field trials collected crop performance data over 4 years, with 10 project partners (Fig.1. A–C). Trials were designed to maximise commercial relevance within the partner’s geographical area. Standardisation was carried out in terms of replication (as possible), use of subplots where relevant, and adherence to standardised protocols. On farm trials aim was mainly to promote engagement with intercropping by ‘Participatory Farmers’, commercial growers subcontracted to carry out trials on their farm, with 42 such trials conducted across Europe.

Crop species and cultivars

Crop species and combinations were synchronised as much as possible between partners and trial types, with special focus on cereal-legume mixtures. Spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) intercropped with faba bean (*Vicia faba*) and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) intercropped with pea (*Pisum sativum*) were the most frequently tested crop species combinations across all trial types. Other combinations were freely chosen by partners to develop novel plant combinations or to match regional recommendations. Cultivar selections mainly followed regional/local recommendations.

Trait protocol

A handbook of standardised assessment protocols was developed in collaboration with research partners to synchronize experimental measurements and terminology of plant traits and agronomic performance in intercropping trials (Kiær *et al.*, 2021; Theilgaard *et al.*, 2018). In line with the aim of these experiments to investigate crop trait plasticity and interaction mechanisms in mixtures, traits relevant both at agronomic and ecological scale were selected. For each trait included in the handbook, method(s) of collection and units were described, and a standard name reported. To ensure minimum data overlap given the high number of possible measurements, traits were classified as ‘essential’ (representing minimum basic data required to achieve project goals) or ‘useful’ (providing valuable additional data).

The protocols developed for use in the plot-scale field experiments were subsequently adapted to produce a derived set of standardised assessment protocols for the large scale trials (Banfield-Zanin *et al.*, 2017). As for the scientific protocols, plant trait and agronomic performance indicators were screened to distinguish between ‘essential’ and ‘useful’ measures in terms of large area production. Attention was paid at this stage to consider the practicalities of data collection at commercially relevant scales, including access to specific equipment across project partners in different geographic regions. Measures also had to be comparable across geographically relevant scales. ‘Useful’ measures were not constrained by these requirements, however, and thus included a broader scale of more detailed assessments. Finally, a further subset of ‘essential’ measures was derived to form the basic data gathering expected of the Participatory Farmers, with protocol text simplified to be as easy to understand as possible with limited or no scientific background.

Data template

Data generated by partners was reported using a ‘Data Template’, a standardised Microsoft Excel file designed to accommodate intercropping data. To facilitate dataset handling, data were reported on different spreadsheets accounting for differences in sampling details. Data relevant to all crops across the plot, rather than individual components (e.g. weed cover percentage) were reported in a ‘plot level’ spreadsheet, consisting of only one entry per plot. Crop-specific data, such as ‘yield’, was reported on a ‘species level’ sheet, allowing two entries per plot in case of mixed plots (or more, if more crop species were grown) or one for monocultures. When possible, data were also recorded at single-plant level (such as for ‘number of tillers’ or ‘seeds per pod’). In this case, data was reported on an ‘individual level’ datasheet, with entries per crop type and per number of plants monitored on the plot. In order to account for regional and year-wise differences in the growing seasons, all data was reported according to Day-Month format, which ensures possible calculation of Days after Sowing (DAS) for analysis. Specific information on plots and treatment levels, such as year, partner, crop and cultivar mixtures and management type, were collected on a ‘plot information’ sheet. Each plot was assigned a unique plot code which links plot information with the data across sheets. A ‘TrialID’ was assigned to each trial in order to guarantee trial tracking across years once the datasets would be combined. Finally, a metadata sheet was designed to report all other relevant trial information (design, plot dimensions, sowing dates, treatment types, climatic and soil descriptions, etc.).

Two additional data templates were designed to accommodate data generated from large-scale and on-farm trials. Both templates had to allow enough structural flexibility to allow adaptation to the specific requirements of each trial, while limiting future compromise for data frame integration. Data template for large scale trials was designed to facilitate integration of returned data with decision

aid tools developed inside the project. A metadata sheet was used to define a ‘Trial ID’, and confirm aspects of data ownership, trial location, cropping information and overall environmental variables. As trial design could not be standardised across the project partners, owing to the need to ensure geographic relevance, a sheet was also included for the definition of trial structure parameters, such as ‘plot’ sizes, management approaches and plant species compositions. Similarly to the template for small-scale trials, data were distributed among different spreadsheets, in particular on ‘species level’ and ‘plot level’. Information on input and output costs was captured on an additional sheet. The Data Template for Participatory Farmers partially mirrored this set-up, although it was designed with the priority of obtaining farmer engagement and return of key commercial-scale indicators. Thus, templates were kept very simple to promote flexibility. A sheet was included to return site-specific information, such as trial identifier, plant team parameters and environmental conditions.

Data formatting

Plot experiments generated a total of 24 datasets for 2017 and 2018 trials. Once these were returned by partners, datasets were first screened for errors, formatting was checked, and partner-specific differences were harmonised. Formatting steps were documented using the open source software R (version 3.6.3, R Core Team, 2020) implemented in RStudio (version 1.3.959). Main packages used for this task were ‘plyr’ (Wickham, 2011, version 1.8.6), ‘tidyr’ (Wickham, 2020, version 1.1.0) and ‘knitr’ (Xie, 2020, version 1.28). Data formatting mainly required name and descriptors standardization (especially among variables that were partially overlapping), screening for evident errors and outliers. During the formatting work, two catalogues were developed. A ‘data overview’ summarised and kept track of correspondence between partner, trial type and level at which traits were measured in each year, whereas a ‘trial master’ spreadsheet was created to track metadata from all partners and years. These files have also been structured by ‘TrailID’, which enables linking to the data files for analysis. Datasets were ultimately merged according to sampling level (plot, species and individual level). Aggregated versions of all levels to plot or species level scale may also be created for analyses.

Results

Thanks to common dataset structure of the plot-scale experiments, we were able to combine datasets from 2017 and 2018, containing a total of 150 traits (a summary is shown in Fig. 2). In addition to ‘essential’ and ‘useful’ traits, many partners also provided extra-protocol measurements, which, in some cases, also matched across partners (with minor methodological differences). These traits have opened further insights on additional relevant intercropping evaluation parameters to be included as additional traits in the protocol handbook. Raw data from small scale datasets is being used for wide analysis across sites and years. A first example is the analytical work on yield stability conducted by Weih *et al.* (2021). Compared to small-scale experiments, large-scale trials had to account for partner-specific designs, which requires higher task input to merge individual templates into a single data frame. However, the common format of the project partner-targeted template should permit this to take place, in line with standard procedures as described above. Summarised data from large-scale and small-scale trials will be used within the framework of a meta-analysis. Small- and large-scale data together also provide the base of further outputs on decision-aid tools to search and visualise plant trait and agronomic information, which are being developed inside the project. To enable data management, sharing, and visualisation, a web-based system, DIVERSiplotter, has been designed to enable efficient querying of crop trait datasets (Raubach *et al.*, 2021). The online platform mirrors the datasets by dividing data into plot, species and individual sampling levels and with a metadata sheet linked to these. This tool will be made available also beyond the framework of the project via GitHub (<https://github.com/cropgeeks/>), ensuring potential alignment of additional experimental datasets, data legacy and accessibility.

Fig. 2. Summary of the eight most frequently measured traits for each crop combination and the range of trait values from small scale trials conducted in 2017 and 2018 in small-scale trials. Raw values are shown for measured traits under monocultures and mixtures of cereals and grain legumes in high- vs low-input treatments.

Data legacy has been further planned via an online Data Catalogue developed within the project framework (www.data.diversify.agroknow.com) and by registering the database in online registries (such as OpenAIRE and re3data.org) and open repositories. However, as no specialised repositories suitable for intercropping data were found, more general repositories were identified (zenodo, dryad and/or PANGAEA). Material used for data coordination and formatting (trait assessment protocols, data collection files and R codes), will also be made publicly available as a resource legacy of the project.

Discussion

The experience achieved in DIVERSify clearly shows that data coordination in agricultural experiments, with specific focus on intercropping, is possible and can enable individual datasets to contribute to collective agricultural innovation beyond the framework of a single project.

We highlight two critical points to ensure efficient coordination in the framework of a multi-partner project. The first is to assign the data coordination work to a specific and specialised team within the project. This will ensure time efficiency in data handling operations. As the quality of the returned data also depends on partners' precision and engagement, the second critical point is to get project partners or stakeholders familiar with data coordination tools, for instance by organising workshops at an early stage of the project to reduce errors during data reporting.

A next step to accelerate access to quality intercrop trait data on a global scale will be the development of international guidelines and protocols for data collection and reporting in intercropping. Tools such as the ones designed within DIVERSify and related projects, should be made available and adopted among projects and authorities involved, to coordinate data capture among stakeholders. This will serve not only to enable faster data alignment, but also to accelerate access and shared outcomes between research and practice. Concerning data legacy, we point out the current lack of specialised repositories suitable for intercropping data. Setting-up open storage solutions specific for this type of data should be the next IT target in intercropping research.

Acknowledgements

We thank the EU Horizon 2020 commission for funding this project, all WP2 and WP4 partners and the farmers for their hard work and engagement.

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